

NOTES

4. K. H. McCORKLE, A. T. KLEINSTENBER, C. E. SCHILLING and D. C. DEAN, *U. S. Pat.*, 3,036, 896, May 22, 1962.
5. N. MICHAEL, W. D. FLITCHER *et al*, Westinghouse Report CVNA-135, 1961.
6. J. LIVAGE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1968, 2, 507.
7. A. G. BOGANOV, V. S. RUDDENKO and L. P. MAKAROV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. USSR*, 1965, 58, 160, 1065.
8. E. CRUCEAN and B. RAND, *Trans. Brit. Ceramic Soc.*, 1979, 78.
9. H. S. MAITI, K. V. G. K. GOKHALE and E. C. SUBBARAO, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1972, 55, 317.
10. N. K. MITRA and K. L. ROY, *Trans. Ind. Ceram. Soc.*, 1972, 31, 82.
11. N. K. MITRA, S. GHATAK and S. MITRA, *Trans. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1977, 76, 6.

Viscosity of Sr(NO₃)₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂ in Mixed Solvents at Different Temperatures

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WATER at ordinary temperature has a quasicrystalline structure. A dynamic equilibrium seems to exist between the three dimensional hydrogen bonded clusters and the denser monomers: (H₂O)_c ⇌ (H₂O)_a. Electrolytes dissolving in water has been classified as structure makers or structure breakers, depending on whether the above equilibrium shifts to the left or to the right. Ions with a lower charge density has a smaller width of region-A in which it is surrounded by concentric region of water molecules, analogous to a kind of freezing and a larger width of region-B, which has got the tendency to resist the normal three dimensional water structure called region-C, and the balance between the two competing forces are net structure breakers. On the other hand, ions with high charge density show an opposite behaviour and are net structure makers¹.

Organic solvents like dioxane, glycol and methyl alcohol are miscible with water at all solvent compositions and their dielectric constants and dipole moments are very different. Dioxane, glycol and methyl alcohol are aprotic solvents, whereas water is both an electron donor and an acceptor. Hence, studies of their aqueous mixtures become an interesting field to explore, particularly of the ionic processes accompanying the solutions of strong electrolytes.

From this point of view, the viscosity of the solutions of Sr(NO₃)₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂ at 10, 20 and 30 weight % of dioxane, glycol and methyl alcohol

have been measured at concentrations, C ≤ 0.1 mol.l⁻¹ at 30 to 45° for dioxane+water and glycol+water and at 30 to 40 ± 0.01° for methyl alcohol+water mixtures.

Experimental

All salts used were of E. Merck, 'extra pure' grade. The contents were estimated in the usual manner. The preparation of the solvents, solutions and viscometric technique were the same as those of Das². The densities of the solutions and the solvents were determined by pycnometer with buoyancy correction and the method is the same as that of Das³. All precautions were taken to check the evaporation of the solvents⁴. The time of flow for each concentration did not exceed by 0.2 sec in about 15 min. Density readings were precise upto 0.0002 g/cm³, i.e. an error of 4 in 10⁶. The concentration range was from 0.1 to 0.001 mol.l⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Viscosity of the mixed solvents as well as those of the salt solutions under study was measured and the results have been analysed. The Jones-Dole⁵ equation $\eta_r = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC$ is found to be valid as the plot of $\eta_r - 1/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear. The intercept and the slope gave respectively the coefficient A and B. The values of A and B, thus obtained, are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

'A' values : The difference of 'A' values (Table 1) indicates dependence of ionic interaction on the nature of the electrolyte and are all positive. The electrostatic ion-ion interaction and hence the value of 'A' is found to increase with decrease in dielectric constant, i.e. when the concentration of the organic solvent increase. It is seen from Table 1 that the ion-ion interaction is of the order Cd²⁺ > Sr²⁺. Further, the value of 'A' decreases with increase in temperature, which one should expect (excepting glycol) in view of the greater thermal agitation at higher temperature and reduction of attractive forces. This, however, is not happening in case of glycol+water as the mixture is more viscous.

TABLE 1
A × 10³/l^{1/2}.mol^{1/2}
Weight % of

Temp. °C	Dioxane			Glycol			Methanol		
	10	20	30	10	20	30	10	20	30
Sr(NO ₃) ₂									
30	10.4	10.9	11.0	14.4	15.2	16.3	9.3	10.1	10.6
35	10.6	10.7	11.8	14.5	15.1	16.2	9.1	9.9	10.4
40	10.4	10.5	11.6	14.6	15.4	16.3	8.8	9.7	10.1
45	10.8	10.3	11.4	14.5	15.6	16.4			
Cd(NO ₃) ₂									
30	12.1	12.6	13.2	16.2	17.2	18.4	10.4	11.2	11.6
35	12.0	12.4	13.0	16.1	17.0	18.3	10.2	10.9	11.4
40	11.8	12.2	12.8	16.0	17.1	18.1	10.0	10.7	11.2
45	11.6	12.0	12.0	16.2	17.2	18.2			

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TABLE 2
B/l.mol⁻¹

Temp. °C	Weight % of					
	Dioxane		Glycol		Methanol	
	10	20	30	10	20	30
Sr(NO ₃) ₂						
30	0.265	0.270	0.500	0.355	0.390	0.530
35	0.270	0.380	0.555	0.360	0.480	0.550
40	0.280	0.430	0.605	0.420	0.500	0.620
45	0.290	0.480	0.680	0.520	0.610	0.695
Cd(NO ₃) ₂						
30	0.170	0.340	0.450	0.305	0.420	0.500
35	0.195	0.410	0.485	0.390	0.520	0.610
40	0.250	0.475	0.530	0.390	0.540	0.660
45	0.315	0.545	0.580	0.420	0.590	0.710

Dependence of 'B' on temperature : According to Stokes and Mills⁶, the viscosity of dilute electrolytic solutions incorporates that of the solvent and the contribution from other sources. They are η^E , the positive increase due to the shape and size of the ion, η^A , the increase due to the alignment or orientation of the polar molecules by the ionic field and η^D , the decrease in viscosity arising out of the distortion of the solvent structure. Therefore 'B' coefficients can be discussed in terms of these viscosity effects at different temperatures.

The 'B' coefficients of both the salts increase with increase in temperature. This indicates that the viscosity decrease due to the solvent structure η^D is small and $\eta^E + \eta^A > \eta^D$ and 'B' is positive. The 'B' value is found to be of the order Sr²⁺ > Cd²⁺ and glycol+water > dioxane+water > methyl alcohol+water in case of both the salts. The lesser the value of 'B', the greater is the ion-solvent interaction. So the ion-solvent interaction is of the order Cd²⁺ > Sr²⁺.

According to Stokes and Mills⁶, the lesser the value of $\frac{dB}{dt}$ the greater is the ion solvent interaction. In the present case, the plot of B vs t is linear and the slope $\frac{dB}{dt}$ is found to be of the order glycol+water > dioxane+water > methyl alcohol+water. So the ion solvent interaction is of the reverse order methyl alcohol+water > dioxane+water > glycol+water.

Dioxane is more basic and less acidic than water because of the electron releasing tendency of the methylene group in the molecule. Water molecules which are hydrogen bonded with oxygen atoms of dioxane molecules become more basic and less acidic than pure water. A cation will interact more strongly with the oxygen atoms of dioxane+water mixtures and an anion will react more strongly with hydrogen atoms. This type of ion-solvent interaction is in the primary solvation sheath.

The addition of small amounts of dioxane may give rise to two effects. If the dioxane is accommodated in the solvent structure, it may strengthen the

water structure because dioxane is a better proton acceptor. If it cannot be accommodated because of its bulky size, it may cause a breakdown in the three dimensional water structure. The 'B' value appears to be less than that of glycol+water mixtures. This indicates that dioxane is not accommodated in the solvent structure and hence it breaks down the three dimensional water structure.

Glycol has two -OH groups and methyl alcohol has one -OH group, whereas water is both an electron donor and acceptor. Methyl alcohol accepts a proton and hence the three dimensional water structure is easily broken. Glycol, though containing two -OH groups, is not able to break the hydrogen bond of water so easily as the -CH₂OH groups are linked with each other. So the ion-solvent interaction order is MeOH+water > dioxane+water > glycol+water.

References

1. P. B. DAS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1981, **26**, 1099.
2. P. P. MISRA and P. B. DAS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, **23**, 1233.
3. N. C. DAS and P. B. DAS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1980, **25**, 725.
4. P. B. DAS, *J. Instn. of Chem.*, 1970, **42**, 70.
5. G. JONES and M. DOLÉ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
6. R. H. STOKES and R. MILLS, "The International Encyclopedia of Physical Chemistry and Chemical Physics", Pergamon Press, New York, 1965, Vol. 3.

Microdetermination of Quinone and Hydroquinone by Differential Pulse Polarography

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MANY polarographic methods have been proposed in literature for the determination of quinone¹⁻³ and hydroquinone^{4,5}. The polarography of quinones⁶ and polarographic application of hydroquinone as a reductimetric reagent⁷ have been reviewed. Determination of quinone by reduction with iodide, and determination of hydroquinone by oxidation with iodine, have been recommended⁸. However, some of these methods are not sensitive, while others are time consuming or require a large sample for analysis.

In an attempt to develop a sensitive and accurate method for the determination of quinone and hydroquinone, we have investigated the application of differential pulse polarography. The present paper describes a method based on the reduction of the